

D4.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable illustrates the Dissemination and Exploitation Plan in the context of the EUreka3D project, co-funded by the European Union within the framework of Digital Europe Programme.

It is a comprehensive document defining communication and dissemination objectives, target audiences, activities and tools for dissemination of the EUreka3D project and preparing for future exploitation. These activities are based on the cooperation of all partners and are strongly linked to the project objectives.

A corporate identity guide and a basic toolbox of templates for the project are defined in this deliverable.

According to the GA, the deliverable is composed of two parts. On one hand the deliverable includes the Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Plan that describes how the project activity is communicated and how the outcomes are disseminated, including analysis of target audience and a marketing plan to specifically endorse the capacity building programme. As the C&D Plan is a living document, updates are foreseen.

On the other hand, the deliverable aims to gather the inputs from the partners about their future plans and commitments for the use of project's results in their own activities after the conclusion of the EU funding period, how knowledge, data and IP will be managed to enable exploitation by parties inside and outside the consortium.

The document is composed of the following chapters:

1. Introduction
 2. Target Groups
 3. Communication Channels
 4. Communication Activities
 5. Preparing for exploitation
 6. Visual Identity
 7. Conclusions
- Annex

1. INTRODUCTION

This report describes the communication and dissemination channels, milestones and target audiences. It provides a selection of tools used to disseminate the results and outcomes of the project, effectively involve stakeholders, and facilitate the exploitation of results and outcomes.

The details about the use of project channels, partners' contributions and editorial publications are described in the following chapters.

Furthermore, the document provides the initial reflection on the exploitation plan that will continue to be developed as long as the project's outcomes are delivered and tested by the partners and by the 3rd party cultural institutions involved as external experts in the project's activities. The exploitation planning is naturally linked with the progress of the impact assessment task and with the definition of the conditions for the use and re-use of the final 3D data sets. The question of IPR becomes relevant when considering exploitation of 3D contents in different sectors of the creative sector, and in particular within commercial ventures. The discussion will continue consistently in the course of the project.

METHODOLOGY

Communication activities aim to amplify outreach and raise awareness as well as engagement by informing about goals, activities and results of EUreka3D to the professionals and general public with the use of tools, such as website, videos, editorial publications or social media posts.

Dissemination activities reach cultural heritage and 3D digitisation networks, especially among cultural professionals, academics, researchers, students and industry representatives, through face-to-face meetings and networking, participation in relevant conferences, workshops, seminars, and other events.

Exploitation planning aims to raise the capacity of European CHIs in their digital transformation through the project outcomes. Experience gained by the project partners during the 3D digitisation process, metadata annotation, and the use of the Pilot infrastructure, will act as a best practice template for CHIs, particularly those who are new to handling 3D. The 3D assets provided by the content partners for the project will be ingested to Europeana for re-use. This includes highly detailed models with complex paradata that will be available for a variety of users from the public to professions including specialists who require but rarely have access to the level of detail that the project aims to provide.

A Communication and Editorial Board is formed since the very beginning of the project, composed by representatives of each partner. The board meets regularly to schedule and discuss dissemination activities, plan editorial outputs, brainstorm topics for editorial pieces and ensure that the publications created within the project are aimed towards achieving the project's goals with an end-user focus. The Communication and Editorial Board is chaired by Europeana and meets regularly every two months.

OBJECTIVES

Communication & dissemination main objectives:

- To give visibility to the project as a whole, within the framework of the Digital Europe Programme and the EU co-funding,
- To showcase the project's achievement and practices and to amplify the project impact in the digital transformation of cultural heritage institutions, specifically in the 3D digitisation field,
- To create awareness about the importance on 3D and 3D digitisation of the past, and reach-out to scholars, experts and any other interested stakeholders,
- To share solutions, knowledge and training materials (within a varied capacity building programme of events and other activities) related to high quality 3D digitisation, processing, preserving on the cloud and sharing of digital collections in Europeana, especially among cultural heritage institutions and professionals,
- To reach out to cultural institutions of various sizes and with different needs, inviting them to access the cloud-based Data Hub and tools developed in the project, also collecting their feedback and requirements and creating a user base of the Eureka3D platform,
- To disseminate the digitised content aggregated at Europeana, in order to promote its use and reuse in other areas such as education or creative sectors and to raise citizens' awareness of the value of cultural heritage.

Communication & dissemination secondary objectives (related to key performance indicators):

- To engage project partners, external experts and other stakeholders with the project's activities,
- To achieve a good positioning and engagement in terms of website, social media and newsletter,
- To reach a relevant amount of CHI and 3D-digitisation practitioners, researchers and educators, with the aim of increasing attendance at physical and online events organised under the project,
- To reach the general public and other end users of cultural collections, mainly through Europeana editorials, project publications and other outcomes.

Exploitation planning objectives

- To promote the creation of basic infrastructure for 3D storage, management and access, also taking into account energy saving solutions,
- To foster technical knowledge from project outcomes and bibliography analysis, for instance by creation of best practice documentation which follow the VIGIE recommendations of digitising and metadata annotation for 3D objects,
- To foster re-use of 3D models by end-users and to define sustainable IP models for commercial exploitation of 3D models within the creative industry,

- To identify and explore challenges with IP and fair sustainability model relating to the technological outcomes linked to the Pilot,
- To disseminate the final booklet of the project (available in printed and digital form) which summarises, promotes, and creates a knowledge transfer of the activities of the project,
- To establish sustainability paths beyond the funded period of the project,
- To support engagement with stakeholders in the education and tourism sectors to facilitate knowledge resources and assist with sustainable cultural tourism.

Outreach objectives described in the *Description of the Action* document:

Editorials:

17 editorials minimum on Europeana

Monthly publication on project's website and other channels

Recipients of project's communication:

200 newsletter receivers

300 followers on the social media

> 20,000 page visits during the project lifetime

Distribution of final booklet:

200 printed copies to key stakeholders + free download from project's website

Others:

Participants in Pilot (project CHI partners, their staff and their networks): overall 50

Participants in the online capacity building sessions: overall 200

Outreach of the EUreka3D Newsletter: addressed to min. 200 contacts

ROLE OF THIS DELIVERABLE IN THE PROJECT

This document serves to establish the bases of the communication channels and strategies and to optimize the resources intended for the communication and dissemination of the project, while following the commitments established in the GA.

The document also defines the initial terms of reference of the exploitation plan that will follow in connection with the impact assessment work.

2. TARGET GROUPS

In this chapter target groups for the communication and dissemination actions will be described. The aim of the C&D Plan is to reach Cultural Heritage Institutions managers, staff and professionals, 3D digitisation and technology networks, researchers, educators, creative industries professionals and general audience, encouraging them to learn about 3D digitisation as a whole (including digitisation, standardisation, long-term preservation, access, storage and sharing) and to appreciate the high value of the content and collections published in Europeana within the project framework.

It is necessary to address each target group with information tailored to its interests and through the channels suiting best the purpose of communication. It needs to be emphasised that the EUreka3D capacity building programme is intended to mainly reach cultural heritage institutions professionals, 3D digitisation and technology networks, researchers, and educators.

PROJECT PARTNERS AND THE EC

Internal communication among partners is described in [deliverable 1.1 Internal Communication Platform](#), where a panorama on the internal communication tools and data protection issues is detailed.

This deliverable specifies additional proposals for internal communication workflow.

The communication with the Project Officer and the EC is based on the specific communication tool in the EC Participants Portal, but also other forms of communication are provided, such via social media by including the relevant tags of HaDEA in posts, and specifically informing the PO about relevant events or activities with media impact.

CULTURAL HERITAGE INSTITUTIONS PROFESSIONALS AND OTHER STAKEHOLDERS

EUreka3D offers capacity building, training, services and resources to Cultural Heritage Institutions. The C&D actions serve to bring these resources to CHI professionals with the vision of the whole value chain of the digital transformation.

The creation of a network of stakeholders who will be involved with the project's activities is under development, through the establishment of cooperation agreements, which include various activities ranging from cross-dissemination, participation in the capacity building programme and other project events, trial and testing of the EUreka3D Data Hub and resources.

Some specific communities are already linked to the EUreka3D project, like ICA International Council on Archives (with more than 2000 members from 161 countries and territories) or the network of Photoconsortium. Members of both organisations are already following the project activities closely.

A dedicated page in the project's website informs about the organisations that connect with EUreka3D and follow project development and achievements: <https://eureka3d.eu/stakeholders-and-collaborations/>

Within the framework of the project, four project partners are content providers for the Pilot programme of high-quality 3D digitisation of cultural heritage, but the aim is to extend the participation in the Pilot also to others, with various levels of engagement.

Finally, an advisory board of experts is currently being established to follow the project's progress closely and provide feedback and advice, particularly about quality of 3D. All partners collaborate to propose candidates to participate in the board. Experts from UNESCO and ICA have been invited together with experts from the organisations that are signing specific collaboration agreements with Eureka3D.

3D DIGITISATION AND SERVICE PROVIDERS

The project works on enabling cloud-based data, metadata and paradata management, in addition to preservation, access and storage tools and resources. In addition, the project is committed to share about digitisation guidelines and standards, particularly but not limiting to the recommendations developed in the EC funded VIGIE Study 2020/654. Therefore, 3D digitisation and data professionals are one of the strategic target groups both for knowledge sharing and capacity building, and in the light of possibly expanding the resources and tools in the Eureka3D data hub.

EDUCATORS, RESEARCHERS AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES

One of the project's objectives is to promote the use and reuse of the digitised content in areas such as education or creative sectors in order to raise citizens' awareness of the value of cultural heritage and to offer a better understanding of the cultural heritage objects. The research in cultural heritage can also highly benefit from the availability of high quality datasets and 3D cultural objects accessible in the Eureka3D Data Hub, which will also publish its services and data in the EOSC European Open Science Cloud to this purpose.

END-USERS

Besides the specific communication actions developed to disseminate the capacity building programme, social media and media communication resources will serve as the main tools to reach end-users. Europeana blogs, galleries and aggregated objects will also showcase 3D digitised content to end-users.

All visual content is of interest of end-users and general audience, therefore Eureka3D project intends to reach a wide audience.

3. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

In the following chapter, communication channels to be utilised in the Eureka3D project are briefly described, after a partners' agreement on the best and cost-efficient communication activities and channels.

PROJECT WEBSITE

[The project website](#) is the main project's showcase and essential to maximize the impact on the project. It will serve as a compelling, engaging and inviting medium to showcase the project and to access the knowledge and resources that the project generates. It needs to be constantly updated and there are foreseen new sections, such as the Impact Assessment Section (upcoming) and a page dedicated to the network of Stakeholders and collaborations (recently published and to be kept updated).

The project's website is created with a Wordpress environment, that is a user-friendly CMS that allows different users from different organisations to easily contribute with content development and publication. The website is managed by CRDI with collaboration of Photoconsortium.

In the home page the most recent news from the project is published, with a list of posts published in the project's blog on the left side and the upcoming event(s) of the project in focus on the right side. A selection of interesting 3D objects sourced by Europeana and by partners decorate the home page and the other pages of the website.

The top menu in each page gives access to the various thematic sections of the website (currently: About, Capacity Building, Resources, Editorials, Project Reports and a link to the projects Blog), which will be expanded as long as new information and content is available.

Screenshots from the project's website

PARTNERS' WEBSITES

Project information needs to be published on partners' websites, updated and linked to the project's website. Partners' websites offer an idiomatic gateway that can facilitate access to the project. The partners are strongly invited to publish news and information about the project's progress in their websites and other channels.

PROJECT'S BLOG

[The project's blog](#), hosted at DigitalMeetsCulture as the project media partner, showcases in-depth content and articles related to the project (events, meetings, capacity building materials...). An RSS feed subscription to the project's website homepage has been implemented that exports all the posts published in the blog into the website Home Page.

The posts in the project blog relate to any news or information about the projects such as: outcomes, documents, participation in events, general news and of course announcement of the activities of the capacity building programme.

Currently, the project blog contains [15 posts about EUreka3D](#). In addition, the project blog hosts news and information from other projects and initiatives that are relevant to the themes of the project, currently 20 posts.

Screenshots from the project's blog

EDITORIAL PUBLICATIONS

A calendar of various publications at Europeana and Europeana Pro is set and agreed with partners. The editorial plan intends to publish:

- [Europeana blogs](#) (4) to show the collections from content providers
- [Europeana Pro](#) (3) to publish articles on high quality 3D digitisation, capacity building and new services and tools.
Proposal on themes: 3D digitisation (CUT), IT infrastructure (EGI), preservation (imec)
- [Europeana galleries](#) (10) created by content providers to showcase aggregated 3D digitised content and some other galleries combining existing content from Europeana and new 3D digitised content within the project framework.

The editorial plan aims to alternate galleries with blog articles, in order to distribute the different kinds of content and audience in the calendar.

Below is a proposed editorial calendar, with tentative publication dates, which are possibly subject to change according to the more general Europeana publication schedule. It is included here to give a first overview of how the editorial publications will be spread out throughout the lifetime of the project to maximize engagement and participation.

THEME	CHANNEL	TYPE	DATE
VIGIE study	Europeana Pro	news post	14/04/2023 https://pro.europeana.eu/post/eu-funded-study-sheds-light-on-3d-digitisation-of-tangible-cultural-heritage
Pre-history of 3D	Europeana	blogpost	July 2023
gallery on 3D in Europeana	Europeana	gallery	August 2023
CRDI's collections of pre-cinema items	Europeana	blogpost	September 2023
gallery on pre-cinema objects	Europeana	gallery	October 2023
Bibracte's archaeological content and tourism	Europeana	blogpost	November 2023
gallery on archaeological content	Europeana	gallery	December 2023

Museo della Carta's heritage collection	Europeana	blogpost	January 2024
gallery on paper collections	Europeana	gallery	February 2023
Cyprus' monuments	Europeana	blogpost	March 2024
gallery on monuments	Europeana	gallery	April 2024
gallery on 3D in Europeana	Europeana	gallery	May 2024
Technical innovation in 3D digitisation by imec	Europeana Pro	News post	June 2024
gallery on 3D in Europeana	Europeana	gallery	July 2024
EUreka3D's cloud-based services and tools, by CUT	Europeana Pro	News post	August 2024
gallery on newly digitised content by Museo della carta	Europeana	gallery	September 2024
gallery on newly digitised content by CRDI	Europeana	gallery	October 2024
gallery on newly digitised content by Bibracte	Europeana	gallery	November 2024
Wrap-up post of the project	Europeana Pro	news post	December 2024

SOCIAL MEDIA

As agreed in the first project meetings, the main hashtag used for communication on social media is #EUreka3D. The contribution from partners in promoting the project's activities on social media is very valuable. The annex of this deliverable provides a table with project partners' social media accounts.

The KPIs for social media is 300 followers by the end of the project. Regular monitoring of the amount of followers will be performed to ensure appropriate progress towards the target, also with support of Europeana social media specialists and with collaboration by all the project partners. At the time of submission of this report (M06), social media are in the early stage after launch.

TWITTER ([EUreka 3D](#)): Created last February 2023, the project's Twitter account is intended to be the network for interaction and professional conversation, mainly focused on promoting project's activities and outcomes. Additionally, it is used for live sharing and conversation about project's related topics.

INSTAGRAM ([EUreka3D](#)): Created in June 2023, the project's Instagram account is the main visual showcase of the project on social media, and it is essential to reach end-users. The feed will share the most visual goals and outcomes of the project and stories will be used to share events, meetings and project's related publications.

LINKEDIN ([Eureka3D](#)): as a professional network, LinkedIn can help to reach a wide but also targeted audience, maximising the project's impact. A company page has been created and initially managed. All the posts published by EUreka3D account can be shared, liked and commented by partners and stakeholders involved in the various stages of the project, throughout their company pages and personal profiles. The publication of content at LinkedIn groups (e.g.: [Europeana LinkedIn Group](#)) is considered, specifically for the promotion of the capacity building programme.

PINTEREST: this social network offers the possibility to create boards for the digitised content and galleries, with links to Europeana galleries specifically created within the project's framework. We consider using Pinterest as another social media tool once the digitised 3D content is already aggregated at Europeana, with the aim of reaching end-users and generating web traffic to Europeana catalogue and galleries.

YOUTUBE CHANNEL: The creation of a project's YouTube channel is foreseen as a showcase of project videos (promotional videos, activities and events edited recordings) and other videos related to the project (using YouTube playlists). A selection of them will be linked from the website and shared through social media on specific occasions.

PRINTED MATERIALS AND PUBLICATIONS

On some specific occasions printed materials will be considered a need, especially when there is the opportunity of promoting the project at in-person events.

During the first six months of the project, a reusable roll-up and a flyer have been produced and printed for [the first public project's event "3D in Cultural Heritage"](#), and a poster and tryptic about the project's Data Hub have been exhibited and distributed at [EGI 2023 Conference](#).

The poster produced on the occasion of EGI 2023 conference

Co-funded by the European Union

Partners:

- PHOTOCONSORTIUM
- CRDI
- Cyprus University of Technology
- unesco
- BIBRACTIC
- CARTA
- Europeana
- imec
- ESI
- CYFRONET

Website: www.eureka3d.eu
 @eureka_3d @eureka3d

Media Partner: DIGITAL CULTURE

EUREKA3D

Eureka3D is the first and unique EU funded project that supports the whole value chain of the digital transformation of the cultural heritage sector. It offers capacity building, training, services and resources to Cultural Heritage Institutions, modernizing their internal workflows and enabling cloud-based data, metadata and metadata management.

The journey of Eureka3D starts from the needs of content providers and arrives to end-users, preserving cultural heritage through high-quality 3D digitisation, standardisation, long-term preservation, access, storage and sharing.

e-infrastructure services development:

- Access to computing and storage resources managed in Europe
- Methods on authorization and authentication with different levels of interaction with users and with Europeana services
- Publication of services on EOSC European Open Science Cloud

The infrastructure of Eureka3D is deployed in CYFRONET-CLOUD, one of the resource providers of the EGI Federation, which uses OpenStack as its cloud technology. Amongst other things, there are three main resources that are managed through the OpenStack platform:

- Computing layer.** The different servers needed by Eureka3D are implemented as Virtual Machines, each of which is managed independently like a physical server.
- Storage layer.** Disks are managed as virtual devices to provide the required storage capacity, and can be attached to the different Virtual Machines as if they were physical drives connected to physical servers. In Eureka3D, the main storage allocation is managed by a service called EGI DataHub.
- Networking layer.** Network connectivity is managed and configured to allow Virtual Machines to communicate. This includes traffic routing (to move data packets from a source to a destination) and firewall rules (to block undesired network traffic).

1) Chapel of Santa Cruz from Brixia, 12th Century. Museo Episcopale di Vicenza, Italy. Digitized by CAUVRIL, Université de Caen Normandie

2) Statue of the Holy Virgin Mary, 18th Century. Museo di Santa Maria della Salute, Venezia, Italy. Digitized by CAUVRIL, Université de Caen Normandie

3) Church of the Holy Spirit in the University of Cyprus, Cyprus. Digitized by CAUVRIL, Université de Caen Normandie

Tryptic (foldable leaflet) produced on the occasion of EGI 2023 conference

More items are foreseen to be created in the coming period for specific needs, such as for example: flyers to disseminate high-quality guidelines for 3D digitization extracted from the VIGIE Study 2020/654; promotional materials for the capacity building programme; informative materials to raise awareness of the EUreka3D Data Hub and resources, etc.

In addition, the final booklet is intended to be the main printed material (200 hard copies) within the project's framework, to collect and share the stories and lessons learned in the project, especially the content providers journey in 3D digitisation, management, sharing. The booklet will also be published as an open access PDF.

NEWSLETTER

A regular project's newsletter is planned to be one of the main tools for communication and dissemination to EUreka3D target audiences. The newsletter will be sent to disseminate project's outcomes and to promote the capacity building programme and project events. The target KPI for the newsletter is 200 recipients by the end of the project.

The next step to build up the newsletter management tool is to work on subscriptions with the partners' support. Mailchimp will be used as the email marketing platform and data protection regulation will be taken into account. The data transferred to the platform will be used exclusively for the purpose of EUreka3D communication and not transferred to any other party.

The newsletter will be sent to the main target groups:

- project partners and stakeholders
- cultural heritage institutions professionals
- 3D digitisation and service providers
- cultural heritage users
- educators, researchers and creative industries
- end-users

Mechanisms to collect subscriptions in the EUreka3D newsletter will be put in place on the project's website (i.e. subscription form) and all the consortium partners will collaborate to endorse the Stakeholder mailing list by inviting their colleagues, contacts and peers to sign up.

The first newsletter is planned to be launched next Autumn 2023 on the occasion of the webinar series, organised in collaboration with ICA (International Council on Archives). The calendar of newsletters to be sent will be linked to the capacity building programme and project outcomes, and the expected amount of newsletters is between 5-6 in the whole project.

MEDIA COMMUNICATION

A media communication strategy will be used to reach general audiences in strategic moments. Two press releases will be launched as a minimum, one in halfway of the project duration collecting the project's milestones and achievements, and another one at the end of the project with final outcomes and the final conference information. Additional press releases will be considered if needed.

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Dissemination and communication activities in the project will focus on engaging ways to share outcomes with various targeted audiences as described above.

Regarding the internal workflow for communication purposes, two points have been agreed among partners:

- The creation of the “Communication and Editorial Subgroup” in order to speed up internal communication.
- The use of the Basecamp Schedule as a tool to share the project milestones to be disseminated and communicated. In this light, partners will contribute sharing newsworthy milestones through the schedule, such as project reports, events related to the project, training material publications, or any other relevant issue to be disseminated and communicated.

A register of the communication actions is being developed and will include dates, channels, audiences, indicators and involved partners.

Since the capacity building programme is one of the core project activities to be promoted and communicated, this chapter includes a specific marketing plan to endorse this programme.

ANALYSIS OF TARGET AUDIENCE AND ROADMAP TO PROJECT PROMOTION

Target group	Communication channels	Actions and tasks	KPIs
Project partners and stakeholders	Internal communication tools: basecamp, mail, zoom	Online and in-person meetings Email correspondence	Meeting attendees Project reports Followers and engagement in LinkedIn
	Social media: LinkedIn		
	Newsletter		
Cultural heritage institutions professionals	Project’s website	Communication and promotion of the capacity building programme	Website visits during the project life-time Europeana Pro visits
	Partners’ websites		
	Project’s blog	Dissemination of the project outcomes and milestones	Europeana blogs and galleries visits Newsletter receivers
	Europeana Pro		

	Europeana blogs and galleries	Promotion of activities and events developed within the project and related to the project	Followers on social media
	Social media: LinkedIn, Twitter	Distribution of printed materials on the occasion of project's events and final conference	Number of distributed printed materials
	Newsletter		Participants in the online capacity building sessions
	Printed materials		
3D digitisation and service providers	Project's website	Communication and promotion of the capacity building programme	Website visits during the project life-time
	Partners' websites		Europeana Pro visits
	Europeana Pro	Dissemination of the project outcomes and milestones related to 3D digitisation, standardisation, preservation, storage.	Newsletter receivers
	Social media: LinkedIn		Followers on social media
	Newsletter		Number of distributed printed materials
	Printed materials	Distribution of printed materials on the occasion of project's events and final conference	Participants in the online capacity building sessions
Educators, researchers and creative industries	Project's website	Dissemination and communication of the project outcomes and milestones	Website visits during the project life-time
	Project's blog		Europeana blogs and galleries visits
	Europeana blogs and galleries	Communication and promotion of the capacity building programme	Followers on social media
	Europeana online catalogue	Dissemination of the 3D digitised content aggregated at Europeana and promotion of its use and reuse	Media communication impact
	Social media: Twitter, Instagram, Pinterest, YouTube		Participants in the online capacity building sessions

	Media communication		
End-users	Project's website	Dissemination and communication of the project outcomes and milestones	Website visits during the project life-time
	Europeana blogs and galleries		
	Europeana online catalogue	Dissemination of the 3D digitised content aggregated at Europeana and promotion of its use and reuse	Followers on social media
	Social media: Twitter, Instagram, Pinterest, YouTube		Media communication impact
	Media communication		

FINAL CONFERENCE AND BOOKLET

The final conference will take place in Girona by the end of the project and is a major project milestone and at the same time a core communication activity. The structure of the event will consist of the following parts:

- Conference open to public on the project outcomes and lessons learned (online and onsite)
- Final training workshop to cultural heritage institutions professionals and 3D digitisation and service providers (online and onsite)
- Dissemination activity open to general audience
- Exhibition of the 3D digitised content within the project. This activity can last beyond the final conference dates.

The main goals of the final conference focus on sharing the project outcomes to cultural heritage institutions professionals and 3D digitisation and service providers, offering capacity building activities, and reaching a wide general audience of citizens and end-users.

The final booklet will be produced (as a PDF and as a printed book) and shared at the conference.

CAPACITY BUILDING PROGRAMME - MARKETING PLAN

Within the communication actions foreseen in the communication and dissemination plan, this deliverable specifically develops a marketing plan to endorse the capacity building programme.

EUreka3D aims to strengthen the capacity of cultural heritage professionals and communities working with digital cultural heritage, such as educators, researchers and creative industries. 3D digitisation professionals and service providers are also considered as a target group in the capacity building programme, since they must be aware of the cultural heritage institutions needs in their digital transformation.

“3D in Cultural Heritage”, capacity building event and first public conference organised by EUreka3D, Roma and online 06/06/2023

The main goal for the foreseen marketing plan is to share solutions, knowledge and training materials through the main communication channels specifically developed for the project. Three principal areas are identified as central topics of the capacity building programme: high-quality 3D digitisation, metadata and paradata management, and the EUreka3D cloud-based Data Hub and services.

The creation of a network of stakeholders through specific cooperation agreements and a more general subscription to the project’s mailing list will be relevant for communication purposes of the capacity building programme. The establishment of these connections with Cultural Heritage Institutions, technology projects and groups of interest will be also used as a way to maximise the promotion of training activities.

Traditionally, in the typical marketing processes of firms and other businesses, the marketing plan starts with identifying consumers' needs and ceases with the delivery and promotion of a final product or service. The core of a marketing plan is usually the development of the so-called “marketing mix” that includes the 4 Ps, the four primary elements which are Product, Price, Placement, and Promotion. While this is not fully applicable in the context of European project, the planning for EUreka3D capacity building and training actions was driven by some reflections on the “customers”, i.e. our target audience; on the “product” i.e.

the training outcomes; the “placement” i.e. communication channels; and the promotion” i.e. the specific tasks.

They are reported in the following table, that shows the current planning and that could be modified and extended according to the needs.

Training outcome (PRODUCT)	Expected date	Target audience	Communication channels (PLACEMENT)	Specific tasks (PROMOTION)
“3D in Cultural Heritage” Capacity building event in Roma and online	06/06/2023	Cultural Heritage Institutions Researchers in 3D for cultural heritage PhD students and educators Other cultural professionals	Project’s website Project’s blog Promotional mail Social media: Twitter Europeana LinkedIn group Printed materials: flyer and roll-up	Production of a reusable roll-up for upcoming Eureka3D events
VIGIE Study 2020/654 (by CUT) materials Flyers and other materials to explain the 3D digitization recommendations in a more user-friendly way	end 2023- beginning 2024	Cultural Heritage Institutions Technology/service providers 3D digitisation professionals	Project’s website Project’s blog Newsletter Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram	Adaptation of the study in a user-friendly way into an online and printable format, to be downloaded from the project’s website.

<p>Webinar series</p> <p>3 online appointments dedicated to different topics, in collaboration with ICA</p> <p>(Programme to be defined)</p>	<p>October – December 2023</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Europeana network</p> <p>Archivists</p>	<p>Project’s website</p> <p>Project’s blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Support from Europeana social media</p>	<p>Opportunity to offer a learning certificate to attendees (using a registration and a learning test)</p>
<p>Training session about the use of Europeana and its 3D objects (in a broader training on archaeological objects and their raw materials)</p> <p>Event in Bibracte</p>	<p>27-29 November 2023</p>	<p>Teachers & educators</p>	<p>Project’s website</p> <p>Project’s blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Promotion of the event in collaboration with Bibracte</p>	<p>Possibility to offer online attendance TBC</p>
<p>Training workshop for “early adopters” of the EUreka3D tool and methods</p> <p>Event in Bibracte or Lyon</p>	<p>End of 2023, early 2024</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Researchers in 3D for cultural heritage</p> <p>Archaeologists</p>	<p>Project’s website</p> <p>Project’s blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Promotion of the event in collaboration with Bibracte</p>	<p>Possibility to offer online attendance TBC</p>

<p>Participation in Mnemosyne Summer School (CUT)</p> <p>Training and presentation on 3D digitisation</p>	<p>tbd</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Researchers in 3D for cultural heritage</p> <p>Other cultural professionals</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Promotion of the event in collaboration with CUT</p>	<p>Need of printed material to be discussed</p>
<p>Training workshop at EGI 2024</p> <p>Participation in EGI conference</p>	<p>tbd</p>	<p>Technology/service providers</p> <p>3D digitization and other cultural professionals</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Promotion of the event in collaboration with EGI</p>	<p>Need of printed material to be discussed (flyers or poster as in EGI 2023)</p>
<p>Training workshop at Euromed 2024</p> <p>Event in Cyprus</p>	<p>November 2024</p>	<p>Cultural Institutions</p> <p>Researchers in 3D for cultural heritage</p> <p>Other cultural professionals</p> <p>Policy makers</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Promotion of the event in collaboration with CUT</p>	<p>Possibility to offer online attendance TBC</p>

<p>Training action at Image & Research 2024</p> <p>Participation in conference in Girona</p>	<p>November 2024</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Technology/service providers</p> <p>3D digitisation and other cultural professionals</p> <p>Archivists</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram YouTube</p>	<p>Edited recordings of the training to be shared through the YouTube channel</p> <p>Need of printed material to be discussed</p>
<p>Case studies on content providers' journey</p> <p>Online publication</p>	<p>By the end of the project</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Europeana network</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Support from Europeana social media</p>	<p>Online format, to be downloaded from the project's website. Adaptation into graphics/visuals to be shared through social media and newsletter.</p>
<p>EUreka3D Data Hub services and tools user manuals</p> <p>Online publication</p>	<p>By the end of the project</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Technology/service providers</p> <p>Researchers in cultural heritage</p> <p>3D digitization and other cultural professionals</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p>	<p>Online format, to be downloaded from the project's website. Adaptation into graphics/visuals to be shared through social media and newsletter.</p>

<p>Eureka3D booklet</p>	<p>By the end of the project</p>	<p>Cultural Heritage Institutions</p> <p>Technology/service providers</p> <p>Researchers in cultural heritage</p> <p>3D digitisation and other cultural professionals</p> <p>Policy makers</p>	<p>Project's website</p> <p>Project's blog</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Social media: LinkedIn Twitter Instagram</p> <p>Media communication</p>	<p>Online publication, to be downloaded from the project's website + 200 printed copies</p> <p>Adaptation into graphics/visuals to be shared through social media and newsletter.</p>
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5. PREPARING FOR EXPLOITATION

This deliverable is provided at M06, thus in the early stage of the project. Initial reflections of the partners about the use of project’s results in their own activities have started, especially in conjunction with the work done for user requirements analysis in the context of the EUreka3D Data Hub and resources development (WP3) and in liaison with the impact assessment task T4.4.

The tangibles for exploitation that can be put to good use can be grouped as:

- The Pilot and its Data Hub, as a storage infrastructure for content providers (currently project partners) to manage their data/metadata, especially on 3D digitized cultural assets. As an accessible storage it will be available to users, with different levels of access to data/metadata. Challenges relating to a viable sustainability model for these facilities are under analysis.
- The 3D assets/models and metadata/paradata. The Pilot in the project will make these resources accessible for reuse by users of various levels and sectors, also via Europeana. This implies the work on integration and interoperability carried out in WP3.
- Knowledge Base - the results of capacity building actions, documents, case studies, best practice, articles, workshop and events, final booklet. All of this should be freely available for use by any interested third parties (stakeholders) and maintained in time. Discussion with Europeana is ongoing for making such resources available in the future Europeana learning platform which would reinforce the sustainability of these resources beyond the funding period.

The dissemination and communication action serves to raise awareness and drive traffic to those tangibles, so that a broad reach and signposting will maximise the exploitation and use of the tangibles.

As a first analysis, a number of project outcomes and their exploitation potential were identified: the elements of such analysis are summarised in the two tables below which show respectively the exploitation potential and the partners’ commitments regarding the various project’s outcomes:

EXPECTED OUTCOME	EXPLOITATION POTENTIAL
High quality 3D digitized cultural objects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To support conservation processes and research • To enable a better understanding of the cultural objects • To complement 2D digitized objects/collections • To enable access by other professionals such as researchers in cultural studies, digital humanities, cultural heritage etc • To enable reuse of the content by others in neighbour sector such as creative industries, tourism promotion, education • To enable the printing of 3D objects, in order to explore new functionalities related to cultural and educational uses
EUreka3D Data Hub – cloud storage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To create a viable alternative to SketchFab and other non-European service providers • To provide cloud services oriented to storage and 3D visualisation for any cultural heritage institution in Europe

EUreka3D Data Hub – metadata handler facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enable CHIs, especially those with no structured metadata management systems to associate meta- and para- data to the objects they upload in the Data Hub
EUreka3D Data Hub – 3D viewer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enable visualization of 3D models, also compatible for Europeana embedding
EUreka3D Data Hub – AAI and check-in	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enable CHIs to profile different categories of users with different rights to view/access/download/upload/update the objects/collections
Knowledge on 3D digitization standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enable CHIs of any size to understand what is high-quality in 3D digitization To help shaping effective digitization programmes and workflows To spread the technical bibliography regarding 3D digitisation and mainly the VIGIE Study 2020/654
Knowledge on Europeana aggregation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To enable CHIs understand the benefits of sharing collections in Europeana and in the Data Space for Cultural Heritage To implement efficient and stable aggregation workflows in compliance with the Europeana Publishing Framework
Europeana editorials (blog and galleries)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To share cultural knowledge and stories that fulfil the mission of heritage institutions To support the circulation of cultural collections across European countries for the benefit of the society and for supporting identity building processes in Europe To create new narratives based on the 3D digitised objects and linked to other content published in Europeana
Europeana editorials (Pro blogs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To share the knowledge generated or packaged by the project to CHI networks who can benefit from it To identify and provide solutions to new technical challenges related to digital transformation
Capacity building programme (events, materials)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To share the knowledge generated or packaged by the project to CHI professionals and 3D digitisation and technical providers who can benefit from it To establish new networks of specialists in 3D digitisation and cultural heritage

EXPECTED OUTCOME	PARTNER COMMENTARY AND COMMITMENTS
High quality 3D digitized cultural objects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Content providers to create such collections Photoconsortium, EGI/AGH, imec and Europeana to disseminate
EUreka3D Data Hub: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cloud storage metadata handler facility 3D viewer AAI and check-in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EGI/AGH to accommodate partners and other stakeholders requirements, with commitment of sustainability (maintenance of the platform in the future) Content provider to test the platform and use it with the EUreka3D collections Photoconsortium, EGI/AGH, imec and Europeana to disseminate also for enlarging the user base (e.g. with associate partners)

Knowledge on 3D digitisation standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Content providers to apply the Vigie 2020/654 Study – All partners to help disseminating and sharing knowledge
Knowledge on Europeana aggregation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Content provider to perform aggregation of the collections in Europeana, with commitment of sustainability (maintenance of the collections online) – EGI/AGH to understand how Europeana aggregation works and the requirements of EDM and EPF, for platform's improvements – All partners to disseminate about the benefits of sharing data in Europeana and in the Data Space
Europeana editorials (blog and galleries)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – All partners to disseminate about the benefits of sharing data in Europeana and in the Data Space
Europeana editorials (Pro blogs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – All partners to disseminate about the benefits of sharing data in Europeana and in the Data Space
Capacity building programme (events, materials)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – All partners to endorse the capacity building programme and to create events, activities and materials.

The discussion on exploitation, also with analysis of IP issues (particularly those linked to the rights applicable to 3D models) will continue in the context of the project and in alignment with the bigger effort deployed by Europeana Foundation in analysing the challenges of IP management and rights on 3D models.

Regarding this latter, it is noteworthy to highlight that in June 2023 partners Photoconsortium and CUT were involved in a broader discussion from the Europeana Data Governance Working Group in the context of the Data Space project, which intended to gather areas on IP management that might need some additional research in order to arrive at a rights policy for 3D models in the future. Because of the early stage of development of the Data Space and of the EUreka3D project a comprehensive view is not yet available about knowledge, data and IP management structures needed to enable exploitation of outcomes inside and outside the consortia of these projects. Discussions will continue and updates on the exploitation plan and task will be provided accordingly in next reporting documents.

6. VISUAL IDENTITY

The visual identity includes all visual elements that can be associated with our project:

- Logo
- Colour palette
- Typography
- Templates for presentations
- Templates for social media promotion (events, conferences, activities, editorial publications)
- Template for newsletter (under development)
- EU emblem

An easily recognisable visual identity of the project is essential to achieve best communication results and reflects the communication strategy and the context of the project. It is of high importance to use these visual tools coherently in the project's website and social media, digital material (presentations, documents), and printed material (posters, brochures).

All communication materials must include the EU emblem (co-funded by European Union). Partners are requested to use the emblem and the project Grant Agreement number in all of their external communication and dissemination materials.

The project's logo in its variants

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Template for presentations

7. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable offers an overview on the Communication and Dissemination Plan and the initial reflections on the Exploitation Plan.

With regard to the Communication and Dissemination Plan, it includes the description of what is to be used for internal and external communication, focusing on the elements that are significant for effective implementation of the communication and dissemination activities within the EUREKA3D project.

At the time of writing, some of the described communication tools are under development (newsletter management tool, YouTube Channel), while others are already active and constantly updated.

With regard to the Exploitation Plan, the document provides an overview for each expected outcome of its exploitation potential and the commentary and initial commitments expressed by the partners.

Considering these Plans as living documents, updates and improvements are foreseen in the next period.

ANNEX: PARTNERS' SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

Partner	Twitter	Instagram	LinkedIn	YouTube	Facebook
Photoconsortium	@PhotoConsortium	@photoconsortium		https://www.youtube.com/@photoconsortium5083	https://www.facebook.com/PhotoConsortium
CRDI – Ajuntament de Girona	@arxiu_gi			https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCaseZybZAAIj3erq_ZbS5QQ	
Europeana Foundation	@Europeanaeu	@europeana_eu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/europeana		https://www.facebook.com/Europeana
Cyprus University of Technology	@CyUniTech @UNESCO_DCH_ERA	@cyprusuniversitytechnology	https://www.linkedin.com/school/cyprus-university-of-technology/	https://www.youtube.com/c/CyprusUniversityTechnology https://www.youtube.com/c/digitalheritageresearchlab	https://www.facebook.com/CyprusUniversityTechnology/?fref=ts https://www.facebook.com/EU.Mnemosyne https://www.facebook.com/Unesco.DCH/
Bibracte	@BibracteBeuvray	@musee_bibracte		https://www.youtube.com/@BibracteBeuvray?app=desktop	https://fr-fr.facebook.com/BibracteMuseum

Museo della Carta		@museocartapescia	https://www.linkedin.com/in/museo-della-carta-di-pescia-0b8b3835/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCX-qu9SvN3dKd6govwlvo0A	https://www.facebook.com/museo.dellacarta/
EGI Foundation	@EGI_elnfra		https://www.linkedin.com/company/egi-foundation/	https://www.youtube.com/c/EGIFederation	
Cyfronet	@Cyfronet			https://www.youtube.com/user/CyfronetAGH	https://www.facebook.com/Cyfronet
imec	@imec_int	@imec_int	https://www.linkedin.com/company/imec/?utm_source=website&utm_medium=footer-social		https://www.facebook.com/imecinternational/?utm_source=website&utm_medium=footer-social